

TEACHING CHUNKS OF LANGUAGE: FROM TEXT TO TASK

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ABSTRACT Language learning has evolved significantly over the years, and one approach that has gained substantial traction is the teaching of language in "chunks." This method focuses on teaching learners fixed or semi-fixed phrases, collocations, and idiomatic expressions as units of meaning, rather than isolating individual words. This article explores the concept of teaching chunks of language, its theoretical underpinnings, practical applications, and the transition from text-based to task-based learning.

Keywords: language chunks, task-based learning, text-based learning, second language acquisition, lexical approach

INTRODUCTION

Teaching chunks of language through text-to-task transitions is an effective method for improving fluency and natural language use. This approach not only helps students acquire and use chunks of language, but also increases their confidence in real-life communication situations. Future research should examine the long-term effects and application of this method in different educational contexts. In order to achieve maximum efficiency and maximum results in English lessons, teachers in the modern world use many different technologies, tools and teaching methods. Today, a variety of information technologies are widely developed, which are firmly rooted in the field of education. This became especially noticeable in English lessons. In a modern school, such lessons are complex, step-by-step, systematic work using all kinds of information means.

However, despite the newest and most advanced technologies, the most effective means of learning is still text and properly organized work with it.

The text is a constructed and correctly organized speech. Working with text develops speech, enriches vocabulary, teaches you to think, find problem situations and ways to solve them.

Working with text involves several stages:

- Pre-text stage
- Text stage
- Post-text stage

Pre-text stage

The purpose of the stage: initial familiarization with the text, formulation of a speech task, reduction of speech and language difficulties in students, creation of a motivating environment for students.

This stage implies preparatory work for the reading process, namely recognition of the subject matter of the text, analysis of various concepts and terms found in the text. A particularly important factor is also the creation of a favorable working atmosphere and a motivational mood for students.

The pre-text stage of working with text is intended to teach students to identify language units, all kinds of speech patterns and be able to recognize them in text material. At this stage of the work, the lexical-grammatical, structural-semantic, as well as linguistic-cultural and linguistic-stylistic features of the text are especially taken into account.

At the pre-text stage, you can use the following types of tasks in your work:

- answers to the teacher's leading questions
- predicting the content of the text based on the title, illustrations, and other text fragments
- answers to text questions, etc.

At the first stage of working with the text material, the teacher needs to outline the task and determine the most important points of working on the existing text. Namely:

- determine the type of text (letter, newspaper article, dialogue, story, etc.)

Determining the type of text is based on the title, if any, the structure of the text, images, etc.

- identify the main characters that can be discussed
- find and highlight, underline unknown words and phrases or words whose meaning can be guessed without using a dictionary
- answer questions about what the presented text might be about, relying on the material that students have highlighted and underlined

DISCUSSIONS

Language chunks, also known as lexical chunks or formulaic sequences, are pre-fabricated pieces of language that native speakers use regularly. These chunks can be idiomatic expressions (e.g., "kick the bucket"), collocations (e.g., "make a decision"), phrasal verbs (e.g., "give up"), or sentence frames (e.g., "Would you mind..."). They provide a way for learners to grasp natural language usage without having to construct sentences word by word. The teaching of language chunks is rooted in the theories of second language acquisition (SLA) and cognitive psychology. Michael Lewis's Lexical Approach (1993) emphasizes the importance of lexis (vocabulary) over grammar, arguing that fluency is achieved through the acquisition of chunks. Cognitive psychologists like Simon and Garrod (2006) suggest that the human brain processes language in chunks, making it easier for learners to produce and comprehend language fluently. In the initial stages of teaching chunks, text-based learning plays a crucial role. Authentic texts, such as articles, dialogues, and stories, are rich sources of language chunks. By exposing learners to these texts, teachers can highlight and extract chunks, enabling learners to see them in context. Activities such as reading comprehension, text analysis, and highlighting chunks help students internalize these language units.

Transition to Task-Based Learning: While text-based learning lays the foundation, the ultimate goal is to enable learners to use these chunks in real-life communication. Task-Based Learning (TBL) provides an effective framework for this transition. TBL focuses on the completion of meaningful tasks rather than the mere practice of language forms. By integrating chunks into tasks, learners can practice using them in realistic, communicative contexts.

Designing Tasks for Chunk Practice: When designing tasks, it is essential to ensure they are engaging, relevant, and appropriately challenging. Here are some examples of task types that can be used to practice language chunks:

1. **Role-Plays:**
 - Scenario-based role-plays where learners use chunks to interact. For example, a customer-service dialogue where chunks like "How can I help you?" and "I'm sorry to hear that" are used.
2. **Information Gap Activities:**
 - Activities where learners have different pieces of information and must communicate to complete a task. For instance, a travel planning activity where students use chunks like "How about...?" and "What do you think of...?"
3. **Problem-Solving Tasks:**
 - Tasks that require learners to work together to solve a problem, encouraging the use of chunks like "Let's consider..." and "What if we...?"
4. **Storytelling:**
 - Collaborative storytelling where learners use chunks to narrate events, such as "Once upon a time..." and "In the end..."

Benefits of Teaching Chunks

Fluency and Accuracy: By learning chunks, students can produce language more fluently and accurately. They gain ready-made units of language that can be easily retrieved and used, reducing the cognitive load during communication.

Natural Language Use: Chunks reflect natural language use, helping learners sound more like native speakers. They provide authentic patterns of speech that are crucial for effective communication.

Confidence Building: Knowing chunks boosts learners' confidence. They feel more prepared to engage in conversations, as they have a repertoire of phrases and expressions at their disposal.

Challenges and Considerations

Contextualization: Teachers must ensure that chunks are taught in context. Isolated chunks may not convey their full meaning or usage, leading to confusion. Authentic texts and tasks help provide this context.

Over-Reliance on Chunks: While chunks are beneficial, over-reliance on them can hinder the development of creative language use. It is important to balance chunk teaching with activities that encourage learners to construct their own sentences.

Assessment: Assessing the use of chunks can be challenging. Traditional tests may not capture the communicative competence gained through chunk learning. Performance-based assessments, such as oral presentations and task completion, are more effective.

CONCLUSION

Teaching chunks of language from text to task is a holistic approach that combines the benefits of text-based learning with the practical application of task-based learning. It equips learners with the tools they need for fluent, natural communication and fosters confidence in their language abilities. By carefully selecting and integrating chunks into meaningful tasks, educators can enhance the language learning experience and help students achieve greater linguistic proficiency.

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